

Learning Etiquette History in an Age of Confessional Ambiguity: Two Islamic Learning Treatises?

ALI MOUGHANIA (Columbia University, New York)

Abstract

The evident similarity between the learning etiquette treatises *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn* by (pseudo) Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Ṭūsī (597-672 /1201-1274) and *Ta'līm al-muta'allim* by Burhān al-Islām al-Zarnūjī (fl. between 576/1180 and ca 640/1242) raises the questions of what distinguishes the two treatises and how divergences between them function. Close reading of the notable interventions that (Ps.) al-Ṭūsī's *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn* represents allows for modeling them as serving the formation of a Muslim learner who is not specifically Sunnī, even if not particularly Shī'ī either. The analysis sheds light on the role of intellectual borrowing and its place in the midst of confessional ambiguity.

Key words: History of ethics • learning • *ḥawzah* • *madrasah* • philosophy of law

Introduction

Contemporary relevance of a medieval treatise

Within the traditional circles of learning in the *ḥawzah 'ilmiyyah* of Najaf, Iraq, the descriptor 'al-Ṭūsī' refers most readily either to *shaykh al-ṭā'ifāh* (the head of the religious community), Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan al-Ṭūsī (d. 460/1067), who is buried in the vicinity of Imām 'Alī's shrine and is greatly responsible for establishing Najaf's lasting legacy as a central hub of the *ḥawzah* (*ḥawza* / *howzeh*) community; or to Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Ṭūsī (597–672/1201–1274), the renowned polymath whose *Tajrīd al-i'tiqād* continues to be a key text for philosophical and

theological study and commentary in the *ḥawzah* curriculum. Many beginners in the *ḥawzah*, however, are introduced—in one way or another—to the latter al-Ṭūsī through a treatise famously attributed to him, summarizing the proper etiquette of learners, called *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*.

The contemporary relevance of this treatise becomes apparent upon consideration of the context in which the treatise’s ideas continue to circulate—within the so-called *al-ḥawzah al-ʿilmiyyah* community. Linguistically, *ḥawzah* can refer to a ‘region/area/side’ (*nāhiyah*) and is etymologically related to the notion of ‘collecting/acquiring/accumulating’ (*ḥawz*). The *ḥawzah* associated with knowledge/study/learning (*ʿilm*) is ‘*al-ḥawzah al-ʿilmiyyah*’. While this phrase has taken on a terminological coinage in the contemporary (albeit relatively traditional) Islamic learning circles and seminaries of Qom, Najaf, Karbala, and other Twelver Shīʿī Muslim hubs of study, the phrase ‘ḥawzah [of the Muslims]’ (the learned among them being the most obvious examples) appears in some of the earliest Muslim supplication literature. For instance, in a prayer for Muslim frontiersmen, attributed to the Imam ʿAlī b. al-Ḥusayn (d. 95/713), one asks God to, “guard their ḥawzah.”¹ In an earlier letter to Muʿāwiya (d. 60/680), his grandfather, the Imam ʿAlī b. ʿAbī Ṭālib (d. 40/661), reportedly wrote about fending for God’s religion/law and/or the person and standing of the Prophet Muḥammad (d. 11/632), using the phrase, “and so God willed it for us to defend his *ḥawzah*.”² When it comes to the contemporary coinage for Twelver Shīʿī centers of learning, although the discussions of recent technical definition attempts are informative, the following description (not a strict definition, but a description informed by this author’s ethnographic insight)³ arguably better captures the range of references to the term *ḥawzah* among contemporary Twelver Shīʿī Muslims pursuing traditional religious learning: The *ḥawzah* is a center of knowledge in the traditional Islamic context, a hub for seeking sacred learning that is meant not only to engage the intellect but cultivate the character of its community members. *Al-ḥawzah al-ʿilmiyyah* is often translated as an Islamic ‘seminary’ of sorts, but it is perhaps more accurately described as a scholarly community of masters and seekers of knowledge, in which membership and rank depend on both scholarly merit as well as upright character, including the observance of traditional etiquette. When used to refer to such a collective network worldwide, the so-called *al-ḥawzah al-ʿilmiyyah* community has concentrated hubs of intellectual activity centered around historical holy sites, most notably the shrine of Imām ʿAlī in the holy city of Najaf, Iraq, and the shrine of Lady Fāṭimah Maʿsūmah (d. 201/ 816) in the holy city of Qom, Iran. Membership within that broader community would depend more on observing its leading scholars’ widely accepted approaches and norms than on studying at a particular location. But the term *ḥawzah ʿilmiyyah* or plainly *ḥawzah*

1 ʿAlī b. al-Ḥusayn ZAYN al-ʿĀBIDĪN al-SAJJĀD, *al-Ṣaḥīfah al-Sajjādiyyah al-kāmilah*, ed. Muḥammad Bāqir al-ṢADR (d. 1980 CE), Beirut: Muʿassasat al-ʿĀlamī lil-Maṭbūʿāt, n.d.: 127.

2 ʿAbd al-Zahrāʾ al-ḤUSAYNĪ al-KHATĪB, *Maṣādir Nahj al-Balāghah wa-asānīduh*, 4th ed., 4 vols., Beirut: Dār al-Zahrāʾ, 1988, iii: 204.

3 I presented the initial sketch of this working definition for the *ḥawzah*, as I experienced it, at a virtual roundtable discussion for Columbia University’s Sharīʿah Workshop in 2020. A primer with a more thorough treatment is forthcoming. Seyed Masoud NOORI et al., “Roundtable Discussion: The Ḥawzah and the Shariah” (Sharīʿah Workshop, Columbia University in the City of New York; Online, October 22, 2020).

can also refer to specific locations of learning in particular (i.e. not just the city hubs, but specific institutions within the city), such that there exist a plural *ḥawzāt* throughout the world, typically wherever there are qualified masters from within the tradition who oversee learning circles, teach traditional texts according to the etiquette/norms of the broader *ḥawzah* community, and foster an atmosphere of intellectual rigor and spirituality. Members of the *ḥawzah* community are continuously evaluated by more senior scholars, peers and, potentially, qualified students, on their intellectual achievement and character, and so formal ‘degrees/certificates’ are not traditionally regarded as the final word on any given community member’s credentials as a *ḥawzah* scholar/student. To some extent, this even applies to written or oral license/authorization (*ijāzah*) of *ijtihād*. That is because an individual’s intellectual and ethical performance would continue to be monitored throughout life for any serious lapses of method or character, potentially disqualifying the person from the license/authorization or any other recommendation/endorsement affiliated with the *ḥawzah*. To sum up a key point here, the word *ḥawzah* is used to describe:

- a specific local institution of traditional Twelver Shīʿī religious learning;
- a community of such learning centered around a holy shrine, including but not limited to the former;
- and/or the collective global community consisting of the former.⁴

The circulation of the treatise which is the subject of this article among the *ḥawzah al-ʿilmīyyah* community, thus, makes it part of a global conversation as relevant to the history of ideas as it is to the ongoing (re)formation of Muslim community members. Moreover, learning etiquettes are, at once, the initiatory and sustaining elements of membership in this global community. The next section will also emphasize how this conversation is by no means limited to Shīʿī-specific relevance within Islamic intellectual history.

ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn and Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim

ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn—attributed to the Shīʿī Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Ṭūsī—exhibits striking similarities relative to *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim* by the Sunnī Burhān al-Islām al-Zarnūjī (*fl.* between 576/1180 and ca. 640/1242). The source-critical remarks below are, thus, merely

4 See Ismāʿīl b. Ḥammād al-JAWHARĪ (d. 393/1003), *Tāj al-lughah wa-ṣiḥāḥ al-ʿarabiyyah*, ed. Aḥmad ʿAbd al-Ghafūr ʿAṬṬĀR, 4th edn., 6 vols., Cairo: Dār al-ʿIlm li-l-Malāyīn, 1987, iii: 875–6. Also consider section ‘6.3.5. The *ḥawzah*’ of the *EL*³ article on ‘Education, General (up to 1500)’ (Sebastian GÜNTHER). For a discussion of technical definitions that have been proposed for *al-ḥawzah al-ʿilmīyyah*, or just *ḥawzah* for short, see: ʿAlī Aḥmad al-BAHĀDLĪ, *al-Ḥawzah al-ʿilmīyyah fī l-Najaf: maʿālimuhā wa-ḥarakātuhā al-ʿiṣlāḥiyyah*, Beirut: Dār al-Zahrāʾ li-l-Ṭibāʿah wa-l-Nashr wa-l-Tawzīʿ, 1993: 86–94; ʿAdnān Farḥān ĀL QĀSIM, *Tārīkh al-ḥawzāt al-ʿilmīyyah wa-l-madāris al-dīniyyah ʿinda l-Shīʿah al-ʿimāmiyyah*, 1st edn., 6 vols., Beirut: Sharikat Dār al-Salām, 2016, i: 92–9. An additional four volumes are expected to be published. For more recent statements, consider, for instance: ʿAlī Ridā al-ʿARĀFĪ et al. (eds.), [Conference Proceedings], in *Muʿtamar al-dhikrā al-miʿawīyyah li-iʿādat taʿsīs al-ḥawzah al-ʿilmīyyah fī Qom*, Qom: Wikālat Anbāʾ al-Ḥawzah, May 7-8, 2025, <https://ar.hawzahnews.com/photo/372945/المؤتمر-الذكري-المئوية-لإعادة-تأسيس-الحوزة-العلمية-في-قم-372945>; Muḥammad ʿAlī BAHR al-ʿULŪM, *Ṣafahāt min tārikh al-Ḥawzah (Āl Baḥr al-ʿUlūm)*, Podcast bi-Tawqīt al-Najaf, interview by Akram al-MURAWWIJ, accessed May 22, 2025, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hVzMaQpe4FI>.

part of introducing the treatise attributed to al-Ṭūsī, opening up possibilities for further examination by interested researchers. Both texts have been influential in their respective Shīʿī and Sunnī circles of learners, and the latter text in particular has been recognized as a key contribution in the history of Islamic writings dealing with the etiquette of scholars and learners (*ʿadab al-ʿālim wa-l-mutaʿallim*).⁵ The two treatises follow the same outline of about 12 sections, representing their shared content, and which can be approximately reconstructed as follows:

- Section 1: The Definition and Merit of Knowledge.
- Section 2: The Intention.
- Section 3: Choosing the Knowledge [to be studied], the Teacher, and the Study Partner; and Steadfastness.
- Section 4: Diligence, Persistence and Motivation.
- Section 5: Initiating [One’s] Studies, the [Course] Load, and the Sequence.
- Section 6: Relying [on God].
- Section 7: The Time of Acquiring [Knowledge].
- Section 8: Compassion and Advice.
- Section 9: Benefitting [in Terms of Knowledge].
- Section 10: Piety in the Pursuit of Knowledge.
- Section 11: Factors Helping with Memorization and Others Leading to Forgetfulness.
- Section 12: Factors that Invite Sustenance; Prevent Sustenance; Increase Longevity; and Decrease It.

Purpose of this study

From civilizational demarcations taken for granted when discussing scientific advancements to sectarian boundaries that are assumed to develop in relative isolation, unacknowledged/underacknowledged intellectual influences continue to have far-reaching consequences on narratives, worldviews, and futures. George Saliba’s work on the Islamic scientific tradition had highlighted problems to resolve, “not only in order to understand the extent to which Islamic science was integral to the science of the Renaissance, but also in order to understand the very nature of the Renaissance science itself.”⁶ Devin Stewart had investigated the sources of *Munyat al-murīd fī ʿādāb al-muʿfīd wa-l-mustaʿfīd* by the Twelver Shīʿī Zayn al-Dīn al-ʿĀmilī [al-Shahīd al-Thānī] (d. 965/1558) as one example of a larger phenomenon, “of intellectual borrowing and adaptation across what were often viewed and continue to be

⁵ For instance, consider Sebastian GÜNTHER, “‘Your educational achievements shall not stop your efforts to seek beyond’: principles of teaching and learning in classical Arabic writings”, in Mujadad ZAMAN and Nadeem A. MEMON (eds.), *Philosophies of Islamic Education*, New York: Routledge, 2016: 72–93.

⁶ George SALIBA, *Islamic Science and the Making of the European Renaissance*, Cambridge/Massachusetts and London/England: MIT Press, 2007 (Transformations: Studies in the History of Science and Technology), 20–22, 193–196; George SALIBA, “Whose Science Was Arabic Science in Renaissance France?”, 1999, <https://www.columbia.edu/~gas1/project/visions/case1/sci.1.html>.

viewed, as rigid sectarian boundaries.”⁷ With a slightly different analytical purpose, the present study examines the function of interventions in another set of learning etiquette manuals—the treatise *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* relative to the work *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim*. I highlight the subtle interventions that *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* represents and interpret them as serving the formation of a distinct type of learner (that is, different than the one likely envisioned by the author of *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim*).

Meaning of “*ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*”

The title of the treatise, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*, speaks to the content of the treatise as a collection of prescriptions for the conduct and comportment of learners. The singular form of *ʿādāb*, *ʿadab*, has been defined as ‘the good form that a valid action should take shape as—whether it be in matters of religion or in matters relevant to reasonable individuals [more broadly] in their collective [...]’.⁸ This is related to but to be distinguished from *ʿakhlāq* (sing. *khuluq*), which can be thought of as ‘steadfast, active conditions (*malakāt*) of the soul, in the garb of which one drapes oneself’.⁹ In other words, while the *ʿādāb* characterize the prescriptible form actions take, and are typically driven into action by *ʿakhlāq*, *ʿakhlāq* describe the stable character traits according to which a person bears oneself well/badly toward feelings. With some reservation (as expected even when ‘translating’ within the same ‘language’), then, one might translate *ʿādāb* as ‘etiquette(s)’ and *ʿakhlāq* as ‘ethics’ or ‘virtues/vices’. Thus, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* is rendered *The Etiquette of Learners*.

As the contemporary *ḥawzah* scholar Muḥammad Riḍā al-Jalālī, who published an annotated edition of the treatise, recounts,

-
- 7 Devin STEWART, “Notes on Zayn al-Dīn al-ʿĀmilī’s *Munyat al-murīd fī ʿādāb al-muḥfid wa-l-mustaḥfid*”, *Journal of Islamic Studies*, 21.2 (2010): 235–70, 235.
- 8 Muḥammad Husayn al-ṬABĀṬABĀʾĪ (d. 1402/1981), *Sunan al-Nabī (ṣ)*, ed. Muḥammad Hādī al-FIQHĪ, 3rd ed., Qom: Muʿassasat al-Nashr al-Islāmī, 1427 AH: 35-36: الهيئة الحسنة التي ينبغي أن يقع عليها [ال] الفعل المشروع إما في الدين أو عند العقلاء في مجتمعهم *al-ḥayʿatu l-ḥasanatu llatī yanbaghī ʿan yaqāʿa ʿalayh[ā] l-fiʿlu l-mashrūʿu ʿimmā fī l-dīni ʿaw ʿinda l-ʿuqalāʾi fī mujtamaʿihim [...]* – I make reference to this definition by a notable inheritor of the Islamic tradition for the purpose of approximating a synthesized reception recognized as belonging to the tradition being studied, on the one hand, and, on the other, to specify the particular sense of the term understood in this context. That being said, relevant studies exploring the conception of *ʿadab* in the Islamic tradition include: Ira M. LAPIDUS, “Knowledge, virtue, and action: the classical Muslim conception of *ʿadab* and the nature of religious fulfillment in Islam,” in Barbara D. METCALF (ed.), *Moral Conduct and Authority: The Place of Adab in South Asian Islam*, London: University of California Press, 1984: 38-61; and more recently: Rüdiger SEESEMAN, “‘Ilm and *Adab* Revisited: Knowledge Transmission and Character Formation in Islamic Africa,” in Michael KEMPER and Ralf ELGER (eds.), *The Piety of Learning: Islamic Studies in Honor of Stefan Reichmuth*, Leiden: Brill, 2017: 15–37, https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004349841_003; Luca PATRIZI, “The metaphor of the divine banquet and the origin of the notion of *adab*,” in Sebastian GÜNTHER (ed.), *Knowledge and Education in Classical Islam: Religious Learning between Continuity and Change*, 2 vols., Leiden: Brill, 2020, <https://brill.com/edcollbook/title/56045>. A future study would compare the contemporary, tradition “inheritor,” reception of learner *ʿadab* works the approach I have opted for in referencing al-Ṭabāṭabāʾī above) with a comprehensive historical survey of learner *ʿadab* reception in light of insights offered by the studies cited here.
- 9 al-ṬABĀṬABĀʾĪ, *Sunan al-Nabī (ṣ)*, 36: الأخلاق هي الملكات الراضحة الروحية التي تنلبس بها النفوس *al-ʿakhlāqu hiya l-malakātu l-rāsikhatu l-rūḥīyyatu llatī tatalabbasu bihā l-nufūs*.

The scholars have extended extensive care to this book. For they emphasize [the importance of] studying it, reading it, and attempting to apply it and act on it. Moreover, in our days of seeking [knowledge], we used to hear the grand shaykhs repeat sentences from its phrases, citing its text as evidence. Perhaps the clearest reason for choosing it and emphasizing it [in particular] is the brevity of its main text and the clarity of its prose, making it easier to understand and memorize for the beginner, in addition to its comprehensive and exhaustive treatment of the most important givens and the necessities of proper education/discipline.¹⁰

Background on the attribution of *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn*

Al-Jalālī further cites the preponderance of manuscripts and early print editions of the treatise, its inclusion in educational collections, and its translations and commentaries, as evidence for the influence and circulation of this treatise.¹¹ Why this treatise, specifically, gained so much traction is likely due in part to the very same reason it is believed to be authored by Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Ṭūsī—in all versions, it is attributed to none other than him.¹²

Complicating the attribution to al-Ṭūsī, however, is the evident similarity between the text of *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn* and the treatise *Ta'līm al-muta'allim*¹³ attributed to Burhān al-Islām al-Zarnūjī¹⁴ (fl. between 576/1180¹⁵ and ca. 640/1242¹⁶). The basic outline of the two

10 Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Ṭūsī (d. 672/1274), *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn*, ed. Muḥammad Riḍā al-Jalālī, Shīrāz: Intishārāt-i Kitābhāna-i Madrasa-i 'Ilmiyyah-i Imām-i 'Aṣr, 1416AH: 17–18. (Translations from Arabic are my own throughout.)

11 Al-Ṭūsī, *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn*, 18–19.

12 Ibid., 20.

13 *Ta'līm al-muta'allim* attracted the attention of Gustave Edmund VON GRUNEBaum and Theodora Mead ABEL who introduced and published a translation of it into English in 1947. See Burhān al-Dīn ZARNŪJĪ, *Instruction of the Student*, transl. Gustave Edmund VON GRUNEBaum, New York: King's Crown Press, 1947. For a review of relevant literature on al-Zarnūjī's treatise, see MOCHTAR AFANDI, *The method of Muslim learning as illustrated in al-Zarnūjī's "Ta'līm al-muta'allim ṭarīq al-ta'allum"*, thesis, Montreal: McGill University, 1993.

14 Apparently in association with 'Zarnūj', which YĀQŪT al-Ḥamawī (d. 626/1229) describes as 'a famous town of Transoxiana [...]'. In his abridged and edited version of Yāqūt's *Mu'jam al-buldān*, however, 'Abd al-Mu'min al-Baghdādī (d. 739/1338) appears to list the pronunciation as, 'Zarnūj'. See: YĀQŪT b. 'Abd Allāh al-Ḥamawī, *Mu'jam al-buldān*, Beirut: Dār Iḥyā' al-Turāth al-'Arabī, 5 vols., 1979), iii: 139; 'Abd al-Mu'min b. 'Abd al-Ḥaqq al-BAGHDĀDĪ, *Marāṣid al-iṭṭilā' 'alā 'asmā' al-'amkinah wa-l-biqā'*, ed. 'Alī Muḥammad al-BAJĀWĪ; Beirut: Dār al-Jil, 3 vols., 1992, ii: 664.

15 Al-Zarnūjī indicates that he heard poetry recited by Ḥammād b. Ibrāhīm b. Ismā'īl al-Ṣaffārī al-Anṣārī (d. 576/1180), implying that al-Zarnūjī had likely begun his studies prior to Ḥammād's death in 576 AH. See: Burhān al-Islām al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'līm al-muta'allim*, ed. Ṣalāḥ Muḥammad al-KHAYMĪ and Nadhīr ḤAMDĀN; Beirut: Dār Ibn Kathīr, 3rd edn., 2014: 41–2; 'Abd al-Qādir al-Qurashī al-ḤANAFĪ (d. 775/1373), *al-Jawāhir al-muḍīyyah fī ṭabaqāt al-Ḥanafīyyah*, Karachi: Mīr Muḥammad Kutub Khāna, 2 vols., n.d., i: 224.

16 'Abd al-Qādir al-Qurashī al-Ḥanafī mentions that this al-Zarnūjī is a contemporary of al-Nu'mān b. Ibrāhīm al-Zarnūjī, who is said to have died in 640 AH. See: al-ḤANAFĪ, *al-Jawāhir al-muḍīyyah*, ii: 312; Riyāḍ Zādeh al-ḤANAFĪ (d. 1078/1667), *Asmā' al-kutub al-mutammim li-Kashf al-Zunūn*, ed. Muḥammad al-TUNJĪ, Damascus: Dār al-Fikr, 3rd edn., 1983: 301.

treatises and many of their phrases throughout are notably similar.¹⁷ Al-Jalālī argues, contrary to Muḥammad Taqī Dānīsh-Pazhūh (d. 1996), that *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* sufficiently differs in its examples and brevity to arguably warrant its reception as an independent text.¹⁸ If one is to maintain the attribution of *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* to al-Ṭūsī then it would be reasonable to assume that al-Ṭūsī was referring to *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim* while writing *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* or that both treatises drew on an earlier work which did not survive in its original form. Conversely, the possibility that the briefer text was actually the original, which might have been elaborated on and then later attributed to al-Zarnūjī as *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim*, is less likely given that one would seldom anticipate motivation to falsely attribute a text to a *less* prominent figure (assuming the purpose of false attribution is to increase circulation by association with the said figure).

While al-Jalālī presents a convincing case attributing *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* to al-Ṭūsī, especially given that it has not been attributed to anyone besides al-Ṭūsī, it is difficult to dismiss how the celebrated scholar of the stars supposedly described ‘knowledge of the stars’ as analogous to disease in *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*. *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* appears merely to summarize *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim* on this, stating, ‘Knowledge of the stars is analogous to illness—learning it is forbidden. [It is forbidden] because it causes harm and does not cause benefit. [That is] except the extent to [which such knowledge is needed] to identify the *qibla* [direction of ritual prayer], the times of prayer and other things—for, indeed, that is not forbidden.’¹⁹ It may be argued that al-Ṭūsī used such drastic language, followed by the exception, in order to keep beginners from being distracted away from their core curriculum with knowledge outside of their specialization or from having a spiritually harmful connection to astrology. While this is possible, it is far-fetched. For the fact that al-Ṭūsī was publicly associated with knowledge related to the stars, and his being sought after for it, is not readily reconcilable with such restrictive language about it. One would have expected al-Ṭūsī to modify the statement or to qualify it by clarifying when, beyond strict necessity, a scholar would explore knowledge of the stars. If it were known for a fact that the treatise is the work of al-Ṭūsī, then there would be a reason to seek to justify the uncompromising statement. But since the attribution of the work to him is founded on the accumulation of clues and an assessment of likelihood, the said statement arguably serves to distance al-Ṭūsī from the treatise. Regardless of the author’s personal identity, the present concern pertains to examining the moves made in *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* relative to *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim* and seeking insight into the type of learner-forming project al-Ṭūsī (or pseudo-al-Ṭūsī) invested in by making such interventions.

17 For a description of the *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* treatise’s contents, see: Maryam MOAZZEN, ‘Shīʿī higher learning in the pre-Safavid period: scholars, educational ideals, practices, and curricula’ in Sebastian GÜNTHER (ed.), *Knowledge and Education in Classical Islam*, ii: 829–35.

18 al-ṬŪSĪ, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*, 21.

19 al-ṬŪSĪ, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*, 61: وَعَلَّمَ النُّجُومَ بِمَنْزِلَةِ الْمَرَضِ، فَتَعَلَّمَهُ حَرَامٌ لِأَنَّهُ يَضُرُّ وَلَا يَنْفَعُ، إِلَّا قَدَّرَ مَا يُعْرِفُ بِهِ الْقِبْلَةَ: *wā-ʿilmu l-nujūmi bi-mānzilatī l-marād, fa-taʿallumuhu ḥarāmūn li-ʿannahū yaḍurru wa-lā yanfaʿu, ʿillā qadra mā yuʿrafu bihi l-qiblatu wa-ʿawqātu l-ṣalāti wa-ghayru dhālik, fa-ʿinnahu laysa bi-ḥarāmīn.*

Analyzing notable differences between the two treatises

Upon a systematic close reading of the two treatises, the following observations appear to be representative of the divergences present. While most of the observations I make note of can be better explained by the interpretive model I propose later here, there are expectedly some observations that can be explained by additional models. For the latter, I offer analytical remarks that, pending future studies, may warrant a complementing interpretive model.

On brevity

The most notable difference is the brevity of al-Ṭūsī's treatise—a brevity he declares is intentional at the beginning of the document²⁰ and which is also an indication that he was likely referring to al-Zarnūjī's slightly more elaborate treatise (if not some earlier shared reference) while writing his own. For example, after noting that the Prophet prescribed the pursuit of knowledge as an obligation for every Muslim, male or female, the two authors qualify this by explaining that only seeking knowledge required to address one's (immediate) state (*al-ḥāl*) is an obligation, but al-Zarnūjī elaborates by providing examples while al-Ṭūsī does not.²¹ This intervention may be interpreted in at least two ways: Firstly, by al-Ṭūsī's day, the scope of obligatory learning had already been consolidated/clarified and the point could simply be summarily made without need for examples. Secondly, elaboration with examples would be left to the instructor's discretion as s/he explained the brief statement for students. The latter consequence would fall in line with a pedagogical choice characteristic of *mutūn* (sing. *matn*), which were highly condensed educational texts often made the focus of metatexts that commented and elaborated on them. The instructor's intervening role would thus be emphasized as that of a companion facilitating the learner's education, as opposed to enabling the learner to focus on learning from books alone without reference to a living scholarly network. Moreover, examples often include reference to an instructor's scholarly network or intellectual genealogy, features of which can be invoked iteratively to serve a sectarian learner-formation project. By omitting reference to specific examples citing Sunnī scholars, such as Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan [al-Shaybānī (d. 189/805)],²² or referring to particular texts,²³ al-Ṭūsī allows the treatise to be appropriated for alternative or otherwise broader learner-formation aims.

20 al-ṬŪSĪ, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*, 55: فَأَرَدْتُ أَنْ أُبَيِّنَ طَرِيقَ التَّعَلُّمِ، عَلَى سَبِيلِ الْإِخْتِصَارِ، عَلَى مَا رَأَيْتُ فِي الْكُتُبِ وَسَمِعْتُ مِنْ أَسَاتِيذِي أُولَى الْعِلْمِ *fa-ʿaradtu ʿan ʿubayyina ṭarīqa l-taʿallum, ʿalā ʿsabīli l-ikhtisār, ʿalā mā raʾaytu fī l-kuttābi wa-samiʿtu min ʿasāʾidhī ʿūlī l-ʿilm.*

21 Ibid., 58.

22 Al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim*, 32.

23 Al-Zarnūjī refers the reader to a book on ethics (*al-ʿakhlāq*) by ‘the martyr Nāṣir al-Dīn Abū l-Qāsim’, saying that, ‘it is obligatory for every Muslim to memorize it [or preserve it] (*ḥifẓuhā*)’, while al-Ṭūsī merely asserts the general principle that it is obligatory to seek knowledge required to fulfill one’s religious responsibilities. The ‘Nāṣir al-Dīn Abū l-Qāsim’ that al-Zarnūjī refers to is likely the Ḥanafī jurist Muḥammad b. Yūsuf al-ʿAlawī al-Samarqandī (d. 556/1161), who authored *Bayān riyādat ʿakhlāq al-naḥs* (abbreviated to *Riyādat al-ʿakhlāq* or *al-ʿAkhḫāq*; perhaps misread *al-ʿahqāq* or *al-ʿikhfāq*). Al-Zarnūjī also refers the reader to Abū Ḥanīfa’s (d. 150/767) *al-Waṣīyah*, which he wrote to Yūsuf b. Khālid al-Samfī (d. 189/805). Al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim*, 35, 45; al-ṬŪSĪ, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*, 60.

On exceptions to omitting names of authority figures

There are, nonetheless, two notable exceptions to this observation. First, both al-Zarnūjī and al-Ṭūsī refer to a ‘Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan’ who would stay up at night in study and when he figured out the answers to intellectual problems, he would exclaim, ‘Where are the children of kings when it comes to these pleasures[!]’.²⁴ Apparently, this is the same Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan referred to earlier in al-Zarnūjī’s treatise—Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan al-Shaybānī. It is striking that al-Ṭūsī cites this example because al-Shaybānī is a Ḥanafī Sunnī authority, on the one hand, and there are no distinctly Shī‘ī authorities referred to in the treatise. Then again, a Shī‘ī reader would likely have no immediate reason to assume this ‘Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan’ is al-Shaybānī—he is not mentioned earlier in al-Ṭūsī’s treatise nor is it common to reference al-Shaybānī in such a text written by a Shī‘ī author (unless in the context of indicating differences among Islamic legal schools). Moreover, some versions of al-Ṭūsī’s treatise add ‘al-Ṭūsī’ after the name ‘Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan’, implying that the scribe understood the individual being referenced to be *shaykh al-ṭā’ifāh*, the leading Shī‘ī authority who passed away in the year 460/1067, or perhaps even the author of the treatise himself, Naṣīr al-Dīn Muḥammad b. Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan al-Ṭūsī.²⁵ Regardless of which possibility was intended by al-Ṭūsī, his move can be modeled as one including a reference exclusive to one school of thought only if it is sufficiently ambiguous and/or can be easily appropriated within his own framework for learner-formation. In other words, it is not too important—for al-Ṭūsī’s intervention to function according to this model—who Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan is, and, indeed, there could be more than one. What matters for al-Ṭūsī is that the learner reading this manual anticipates and experiences the enjoyment of intellectual delights available to those who stay up at night to resolve intellectual problems.

The second notable exception to al-Ṭūsī’s omission of specific examples pertains to the citation of an influential text related to medicine. At the end of their treatises, both al-Zarnūjī and al-Ṭūsī urge the reader to engage in learning something about medicine and to be blessed ‘by the reports [attributed to the Prophet] about medicine, which have been compiled by Abū al-‘Abbās al-Mustaghfirī [d. 432/1041] in his *Ṭibb al-Nabī* [*The Prophet’s Medicine*]’.²⁶ Al-Ṭūsī citing a Ḥanafī scholar’s compilation of reports ascribed to the Prophet supports the argument that his treatise is meant to serve beyond sectarian boundaries, on the one hand, and that he is modeling for his readers the ideal of seeking useful knowledge wherever it may originate. Thus, al-Ṭūsī can be read as attempting to strike a balance between his stated purpose of describing a summary of learner etiquette, and his selectivity as it plays out in making his treatise less sectarian while modeling inclusivity toward useful knowledge beyond his own school affiliation.

24 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 106; al-ṬŪSĪ, *‘Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 110: كان محمد بن الحسن إذا سهر الليالي: *kāna Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan ‘idhā saḥira l-layālī wa-nḥallat lahū l-mushkilātu yaqūlu ‘ayna ‘abnā’u l-mulūki min hādhihi l-ladhdhāt*.

25 Āghā Buzurg al-ṬIHRĀNĪ, *al-Dharī‘a ‘ilā taṣānīf al-Shī‘a*, 3rd edn, 26 vols., Beirut: Dār al-‘Aḍwā’, 1983, i: 27.

26 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 137–8; al-ṬŪSĪ, *‘Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 149–50: ولا بد أن يتعلم شيئاً من: *wa-lā budda l-ṭibb wa-yitbarak bil-āthār al-wārda fī l-ṭibb al-shaykh al-imām Abū al-‘abbās al-mustaghfirī fī kitābihi l-musammā Ṭibbu al-Nabī*.

On communal obligation

When it comes to a communal obligation (*farḍ ‘alā sabīl al-kifāyah*), if there is no one in the area to carry it out sufficiently well, al-Zarnūjī notes that all the area’s inhabitants share the fault/sin (*al-ma’tham*). Moreover, al-Zarnūjī states that it is the Imām’s obligation to order the area’s people to step up to the plate and to have them fulfill it.²⁷ Al-Ṭūsī, on the other hand, uses arguably more precise language, stating that if there is no one in the area to carry it out sufficiently well, then they all share (in the obligation) to attain the necessary competence. Assuming this is an intentional edit on al-Ṭūsī’s part, he is making a distinction between affirming a collective responsibility and assuming everyone to be sinful unless it is carried out. That is, perhaps al-Ṭūsī is entertaining the possibility that some or even all inhabitants might in some scenarios have a reasonable excuse, pardoning them from the burden or fault/sin of not carrying out the communal obligation. This does not conflict with stating that the inhabitants, theoretically, share the responsibility to attain the said knowledge. Furthermore, al-Ṭūsī omits any mention of the Imām’s responsibility, perhaps reflecting his conviction that the Imām (in Shīrī Islam) is not to be taught his responsibility—the immaculate Imām knows his own duties, whether it be a time of presence (i.e. *ḥuḍūr*, in which he is generally accessible to the public) or absence (i.e. *ghaybah*, in which he is generally inaccessible to the public and acts from behind the scenes).²⁸

On intention

On the importance of having a righteous intention for seeking knowledge, both al-Zarnūjī and al-Ṭūsī quote the Prophet as having said, ‘Deeds are but by intentions’.²⁹ But although al-Zarnūjī comments that this is an authentic (*ṣaḥīḥ*) ḥadīth attributed to the Prophet, al-Ṭūsī omits such an evaluation. This omission speaks to the approach taken by al-Ṭūsī when it comes to benefiting from ḥadīth in non-legal matters. For when there is no legal ruling at stake, ḥadīth authenticity/reliability in terms of chain of transmission (*isnād*) no longer carries much weight. It is, rather, the soundness of the content (*matn*) that is paramount. Al-Ṭūsī may have assumed it sufficiently evident from first principles, sound reasoning and/or established Islamic teachings that this quote’s content is sound, and that the characterization of its chain of transmission is unwarranted for the purposes at hand.³⁰ Such an intervention,

27 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 35: وأما حفظ ما يقع في الأحايين؛ ففرض على سبيل الكفاية، إذا قام به البعض (في بلدة) سقط عن الباقي، فإن لم يكن في البلدة من يقوم به اشتركوا جميعاً في المأثم، ويجب على الإمام أن يأمرهم بذلك، ويجبر أهل البلدة على ذلك *wa-’ammā ḥifzu mā yaqa’u fī l-’aḥyā’ini fā-farḍun ‘alā sabīli l-kifāyati, ‘idhā qāma bihi l-ba’du fī baldatin saqaṭa ‘an il-bāqīn, fā-’in lam yakun fī l-baldati man yaqūmu bihi shtarakū jamī’an fī l-ma’tham, wa-yajibū ‘alā l-’imāmi ‘an ya’murāhum bi-dhālik, wa-yujbira ‘ahla l-baldati ‘alā dhālik.*

28 al-ṬŪSĪ, *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 60: والذي يكون الاحتياج إليه في الأحيان فرض على سبيل الكفاية إذا قام به البعض (في بلدة) سقط عن الباقي، وإن لم يكن في البلد من يقوم به اشتركوا جميعاً - بتخصيله، بالوجوب *wa-’lādhi yakūnu l-iḥtīyāju ‘alayhi fī l-’aḥyā’ini farḍun ‘alā sabīli l-kifāyati ‘idhā qāma bihi l-ba’du saqaṭa ‘an il-bāqīn, wa-’in lam yakun fī l-baladi man yaqūmu bihi shtarakū - jamī’an - bi-taḥṣīlihi bi-l-wujūb.*

29 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 39; al-ṬŪSĪ, *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 63: إنما الأعمال بالنيات *innamā al-’a’mālu bi-l-niyyāt.*

30 It is also possible that al-Ṭūsī omitted an evaluation of the ḥadīth’s reliability because it was obvious and/or widely recognized as a mutawātir or otherwise verifiably certain account of the Prophet’s words.

despite being an omission, arguably serves as a reaffirmation of al-Ṭūsī's approach to ḥadīth in non-legal contexts, aimed at training the learner to adopt that approach or at least follow up with the instructor on relevant concerns.

On prioritizing

Al-Zarnūjī and al-Ṭūsī agree that a learner should prioritize his/her intellectual pursuits, electing the best knowledge that addresses his/her most immediate religious needs. Of these needs, 'the knowledge of [Divine] Oneness (*al-tawḥīd*) comes first, and s/he is to know God Almighty with proof'.³¹ But al-Ṭūsī omits al-Zarnūjī's comment that, 'even though the faith of a blind follower (*muqallid*)³² is valid in our view, such an individual would be sinful for the neglect of reasoning'.³³ This is arguably more than an omission for the sake of brevity, on al-Ṭūsī's part. Whether or not al-Ṭūsī agrees with al-Zarnūjī's position on the validity of *taqlīd* in fundamental matters of faith, al-Ṭūsī clearly does not want learners to commit such a nuanced position to memory in the beginning of their studies. Instead, al-Ṭūsī's emphasis is on reasoning/argumentation that leads to proof. This intellectual skill embedded in a text on learning etiquette, intentionally brief to be more easily committed to memory, can be modeled as speaking to al-Ṭūsī's concern for the cultivation of a particular type of subject—one who keeps his/her eyes on the ball of the evidence/proof, even from the earliest stages of study. Moreover, such an interpretation resonates well with al-Ṭūsī's comment on condensed educational texts (*mutūn*), apparently absent from al-Zarnūjī's treatise. As al-Ṭūsī writes, '[the learner] should choose [to study] the [condensed educational] texts'.³⁴ As it has been said, 'stick to³⁵ the [condensed educational] texts'.³⁶ This note speaks to al-Ṭūsī's likely preference that learners form themselves by engaging with core texts closely and reflectively, without allowing commentaries to limit/skew their independent engagement with the content.

On steadfastness

On steadfastness, both al-Zarnūjī and al-Ṭūsī emphasize the need to be patient, sticking to one's (properly selected) teacher, book, art/craft, and area. However, al-Ṭūsī makes a subtle modification of al-Zarnūjī's prescription about not embarking 'on another art before perfecting (*yutqīn*) [the first one]'.³⁷ Al-Ṭūsī, perhaps anticipating that this expression would

31 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'īlīm al-muta'allim*, 47; al-ṬŪSĪ, *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn*, 67: وَيَعْرِفُ اللَّهُ تَعَالَى وَيُقَدِّمُ عِلْمَ التَّوْحِيدِ، وَبِإِلْمِ اللَّهِ تَعَالَى بِالذَّلِيلِ *wa-yuqaddima 'ilma l-tawḥīd, wa-ya'rifa llāha ta'ālā bil-dalīl*.

32 In different contexts, the notion of *taqlīd* and the practitioner, *muqallid*, signify the practice of referring to expert research, and the practitioner who does so, respectively. This is widely regarded as valid in legal matters but invalid in fundamental matters of belief (the latter being invalid unless the reference to such research is merely used as a catalyst for the practitioner's independent reasoning to arrive at his/her beliefs).

33 Al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'īlīm al-muta'allim*, 47: وَلَكِنْ يَكُونُ أَمَّا بَرَكِ الْإِسْتِدْلَالِ *fa-'inna 'imāna l-muqallidi wa-'in kāna ṣaḥīḥan 'indanā, wa-lākin yakūnu 'āthiman bi-tarḥi l-istidlāl*.

34 As opposed to commentaries or expositions, for instance.

35 *'alaykum*; the preposition and pronoun in this context serve to call the person addressed toward the action.

36 al-ṬŪSĪ, *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn*, 68: "عَلَيْكُمْ بِالْمُتُونِ" . كَمَا قِيلَ "عَلَيْكُمْ بِالْمُتُونِ" *wa-yakhtāra l-mutūn. Kamā qīla: "alaykum bi-l-mutūn."*

37 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'īlīm al-muta'allim*, 51: وَعَلَى فَنٍ ، حَتَّى لَا يَشْتَغَلَ بِنَاقِظٍ آخَرَ قَبْلَ أَنْ يَتَقَنَّ الْأَوَّلَ *wa-'alā fann, ḥattā lā yashṭaghila bi-fannin 'ākhara qabla 'an yutqīna l-'awwal*.

debilitate beginners who may unreasonably obsess over ‘perfecting’ their knowledge of one field before moving on to another, waters down the expression to be ‘on another art before becoming skilled (*māhir*) [at the first one]’.³⁸ Furthermore, on the motives behind remaining steadfast, al-Zarnūjī reasons that the contrary would ‘distract one from attaining knowledge, preoccupy the heart, waste time, and hurt the teacher’.³⁹ Al-Ṭūsī does not mention, ‘and hurt the teacher’, likely because his emphasis on having the learner cultivate his/her dispositions regardless whether or not the teacher has the appropriate concern for the learner’s wellbeing or not. Moreover, al-Ṭūsī omits al-Zarnūjī’s mention of patience in the sense of resisting one’s own whims, and being patient in the face of hardships, perhaps because such ethical prescriptions are not specific to learners but extend to all.

On venerating knowledge

On venerating knowledge and its people, the treatise attributed to al-Ṭūsī appears to water down al-Zarnūjī’s emphasis on manifest expressions of esteem, arguably beyond merely summarizing. For al-Zarnūjī makes success in attaining knowledge contingent on one’s esteem for knowledge, generally, and one’s own teacher, specifically. While al-Ṭūsī emphasizes esteem in one’s heart, stating that ‘[the learner] should esteem knowledge and its people in the heart with the highest esteem’,⁴⁰ al-Zarnūjī goes as far as to summarize the following principles manifested in action, not merely in the heart, writing: ‘In summary: [the learner] should seek [the teacher’s] satisfaction; avoid his displeasure; and obey his command so long as it is not to disobey God Almighty—there is no [due] obedience to a creature in disobeying the Creator!’⁴¹ Al-Zarnūjī extends expression of veneration even to the teacher’s children and those associated with the teacher, recounting stories of scholars exemplifying such esteem.⁴² Specifically when it comes to expressions of esteem for one’s teacher, al-Ṭūsī appears less willing to preserve the same examples that al-Zarnūjī recounts. This speaks to al-Ṭūsī’s likely concern for a learner’s formation with an esteem for knowledge and its people but without going beyond context-based norms to that end. That is, al-Ṭūsī either disagrees with some of al-Zarnūjī’s promoted expressions of veneration (e.g. requiring general obedience to the teacher) or otherwise simply refuses to enshrine such examples of veneration in a treatise that will last perpetually. Al-Ṭūsī’s summary allows for context-based expressions of veneration and arguably contributes to shaping a different type of learner, one who holds esteem in his/her heart but only expresses it according to the norms/customs of the changing times/places. Then again, al-Ṭūsī does agree with al-Zarnūjī on specific

38 al-ṬŪSĪ, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*, 69: *wa-ʿalā fann, ḥattā lā yashṭaghila bi-fannin ākhara qabla ʿan yaṣīra māhiran fīh. حتى لا يشتغل بفن آخر قبل أن يصير ماهرا فيه*.

39 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim*, 52: *fa-ʾinna dhālika kullu yufarriqu l-ʾumūr, wa-yushghilu l-qalb, wa-yuḍayyiʿu l-ʾawqāt, wa-yuʾdhī l-muʿallim. فإن ذلك كله يفرق الأمور، ويشغل القلب، ويضيع الأوقات، ويؤذي المعلم*.

40 al-ṬŪSĪ, *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*, 72: *wa-yanbaghī ʾan yuʿazzima l-ʾilma wa-ʾahlahu bi-l-qalbi ghāyata l-taʿzīm. وينبغي أن يعظم العلم وأهله بالقلب غاية التعظيم*.

41 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Taʿlīm al-mutaʿallim*, 56: *fa-lḥaṣil: ʾannahu yaṭlubu riḍāh, wa-yajtanibu sakhaṭah, wa-yamtathilu ʾamrahu min ghayri maʾṣiyati llāhi taʾālā, wa-lā ṭāʾata lil-makhlūqī fī maʾṣiyati l-khāliq! فالحاصل: أنه يطلب رضاه، ويجتنب سخطه، ويمتثل أمره من غير معصية الله تعالى، ولا طاعة للمخلوق في معصية الخالق!*

42 Ibid., 56–61.

examples of veneration, such as not sitting '[too] close to the teacher during class [or when s/he arrives before others], unless out of necessity. Rather, between [the learner] and the teacher there should be [at least] a bow's length. For that is a better expression of esteem'.⁴³ While this observation strengthens the possibility that al-Ṭūsī simply disagrees with al-Zarnūjī on the types of veneration he does not mention, it is still conceivable that the culture of veneration is so ingrained in him that al-Ṭūsī allows some context-specific examples to appear timeless and, thus, he includes them without hesitation in his treatise.

On maintaining energy levels and discouraging excessive consumption

The two treatises are apparently in agreement on a correlation between laziness and excessive phlegm and liquids, describing the means to reducing the latter by: reducing one's food consumption; brushing one's teeth (*al-siwāk*⁴⁴); and simply coughing it up.⁴⁵ They both mention that eating dry bread, on the one hand, and eating raisins [on an empty stomach]⁴⁶ (in moderation, lest it require more water intake), on the other hand, reduce phlegm, but only al-Zarnūjī refers to a quote attributed to Galen (d. ca. 200 CE) saying, 'Pomegranate, in its entirety, is beneficial, while fish, in its entirety, is harmful', and follows it up with a saying that goes, 'Fish is better than excessive pomegranate'.⁴⁷ Perhaps al-Ṭūsī found no credence to the attribution of the former and/or medical knowledge in his day had discredited either the former or the latter. Regardless, neglecting mention of such advice would be expected to function as influential in shaping the eating habits of learners and perhaps even their purchasing habits, thereby contributing to learner-formation in a compound fashion (i.e. as a cultivated habit for ethical reasons as well as a spending/consumption routine). The two treatises also agree on the means for reducing one's food consumption, such as: reflecting on the benefits of reduced food consumption; reflecting on the harms of excessive food consumption; eating rich foods, prioritizing that which one finds most pleasant and has the most appetite for; and not to seek out food consumption and sleep except for the purpose of strengthening oneself to perform acts of obedience to God, such as fasting, prayer and other things.⁴⁸ But although both al-Zarnūjī and al-Ṭūsī mention the beneficial themes of reducing food consumption (e.g. health and chastity) and the harmful themes of excessive food consumption (e.g. illnesses, lethargy and reduced wit), it is al-Zarnūjī's specific examples that arguably drive the points home in ways that the brief treatise attributed to al-Ṭūsī (without such examples) does not. For instance, al-Zarnūjī refers to a quote attributed to the

43 Ibid., 65: وينبغي لطالب العلم ألا يجلس قريباً من الأستاذ عند السبق بغير ضرورة، بل ينبغي أن يكون بينه وبين الأستاذ قدر: *wa-yanbaghī li-ṭālibi l-'ilmi 'allā ['an lā] yajlisa qarīban min al-'ustādhi 'inda l-sabqi bi-ghayri ḍarūra, bal yanbaghī 'an yakūna baynahu wa-bayna l-'ustādhi qadru l-qaws, fa-'innahu 'aqrabu 'ilā l-ta'zīm.*

44 Or, more specifically, an instrument made of wood from the *arāk* tree, used as a toothbrush, also called *miswāk*. It likely refers specifically to this type of wood because both authors later warn against using just any wood to clean teeth: al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'lim al-muta'allim*, 133; al-ṬŪSĪ, *'Adāb al-muta'allimīn*, 139.

45 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'lim al-muta'allim*, 81; al-ṬŪSĪ, *'Adāb al-muta'allimīn*, 87.

46 According to al-Zarnūjī. al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'lim al-muta'allim*, 81.

47 Ibid., 82: الرمان نافع كله، والسمك ضار كله . وقيل: السمك خير من كثير الرمان *al-rummānu nāfi'un kulluh, wa-l-samaku ḍārrun kulluh. wa-qīla: al-samaku khayrun min kathīri r-mān.*

48 Ibid., 82–3; al-ṬŪSĪ, *'Adāb al-muta'allimīn*, 88–9.

Prophet Muḥammad in which he states that ‘there are three [types of individuals] whom God Almighty dislikes⁴⁹ even when they have not committed a crime: the excessive eater; the stingy; and the arrogant’.⁵⁰ Al-Zarnūjī also writes the following as if it is proverbial: ‘The excessive eater is disliked by the hearts’.⁵¹ In addition to aiming for brevity, it is likely that al-Ṭūsī did not find any extant Shī‘ī references compiling these quotes and others. This is not to say that the principle did not hold true in some sense for al-Ṭūsī, but that he likely did not want to give the impression of invoking Prophetic authority when there was no long-standing reference indicating that the Prophet had said such a thing in those words. Just the same, because al-Ṭūsī does not draw attention to these images of dislike, his readers are not anticipated to be equipped (on account of the treatise alone) with this additional tool of learner-formation that al-Zarnūjī’s readers would have from his treatise. Granted, this is another instance in which the teacher’s explanations may have been envisioned to fill in with such examples instead of explicit mention in the treatise attributed to al-Ṭūsī.

On seeking knowledge alongside livelihood

One interesting departure of the treatise attributed to al-Ṭūsī from that associated with al-Zarnūjī arguably appears in the latter’s comments on seeking beneficial learning throughout one’s daily life (beyond the formal class session). While both authors emphasize that the seeker of knowledge should at all times and in all states be seeking beneficial learning from all individuals, quoting the Prophet as having said: ‘Wisdom is the lost item of the believer—wherever s/he finds it, s/he takes it [back]’,⁵² and referencing a saying that goes: ‘Take what is pure and leave what is impure’,⁵³ only al-Zarnūjī makes it explicit that ‘seeking knowledge and understanding (*fiqh*) can be combined with gaining a livelihood (*al-kasb*) [through a profession/trade]’.⁵⁴ Al-Zarnūjī makes this conclusion after referring to how Abū Ḥanīfa (d. 150/767) became learned by extensive discussion and study in his shop while he worked as a cloth merchant (*bazzāz*). That being said, the treatise attributed to al-Ṭūsī does include the general statement, also in al-Zarnūjī’s version: ‘One with a sound body and mind has no excuse to abandon learning’.⁵⁵ Both treatises also remind us that ‘in the old days, they used to learn a craft/trade (*al-ḥirfah*), and then they would learn the knowledge [of the religion]—

49 When love/hate is mentioned in the context of God, who is beyond the emotional limitations of creatures, it is typically understood as an expression of how spiritually ‘close’ the object of love/hate is to God’s excellence. This naturally has expressions in the world of creation—manifestations representing His satisfaction/displeasure.

50 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 82: الأكل، والبخل، والمتكبر: الثلاثة ييغضهم الله تعالى من غير جرم: الأكل، والبخل، والمتكبر: *thalāthatun yubghiduhum-u llāhu ta’ālā min ghayri jurmin: al-’akūl, wa-l-bakhīl, wa-l-mutakabbir.*

51 Ibid., 83: والأكل بغيض في القلوب *wa-l-’akūlu baghīḍun fī l-qulūb*

52 Ibid., 92; al-ṬŪSĪ, *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 99: الحكمة ضالة المؤمن أينما وجدها أخذها *al-ḥikmatu ḍāllatu l-mu’mini ’aynamā wajadahā ’akhadhahā.*

53 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 92; al-ṬŪSĪ, *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 99–100: خذ ما صفا ودع ما كدر *khudh mā ṣafā wa-da’ mā kadara.*

54 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 94: في هذا يعلم: أن تحصيل العلم والفقه يجتمع مع الكسب *fa-bi-hādhā yu’lamu: ’anna taḥṣīla l-’ilmi wa-l-fiqhi yajtami’u ma’a l-kasb.*

55 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 110; al-ṬŪSĪ, *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 100: وليس لصحيح البدن والعقل عذر في ترك التعلم *wa-laysa li-ṣaḥīḥi l-badani wa-l-’aqli ’udhrun fī tarki l-ta’allum.*

so that they would not be after people's wealth.⁵⁶ But in the context of al-Ṭūsī's treatise, without al-Zarnūjī's examples (or similar ones) to reference masters working for a living while learning, such a statement is arguably bereft of any serious emphasis on learners seeking their own livelihood through a craft/trade (as opposed to being supported through stipends funded by religious endowments, donations and the like). In other words, al-Zarnūjī's examples seem to paint the picture of not only one who learns (at whatever pace) while his/her primary objective is to function as a professional in his/her craft/trade but also one who works while his/her primary objective is to be a learner (on the path of rigorous, specialist training). Regardless whether al-Ṭūsī (or another presumed author) consciously omitted reference to examples implying the latter, the omission appears to function as a rule of thumb for learners (whose primary objective is to be specialists in their knowledge) that their time/energy should ideally be focused as much as possible on learning—even though other members of society are still expected to seek knowledge to some extent alongside pursuing their primary crafts/trades. This much has clearly become the norm gradually if not in al-Ṭūsī's day, as evidenced by the contemporary model for financially supporting the pursuit of knowledge in *hawzah* circles (i.e., where students and teachers alike are able to dedicate themselves to studies and other devotional activities full-time thanks to religiously administered housing options and stipends for living expenses).⁵⁷ Thus, in the rendering of the treatise attributed to al-Ṭūsī, albeit subtly, the learner is steered away from seriously considering the feasibility of engaging in a craft/trade while pursuing specialist learning. This may speak to a shift in specialization norms promoted by al-Ṭūsī (and/or those circulating the *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn* treatise) and, subsequently, a different formation program for the specialist-to-be.

Shī'īfying or de-Sunnīfying?

It may be tempting to assume that the author of *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn* is 'Shī'īfying' (making Shī'ī) al-Zarnūjī's *Ta'līm al-muta'allim* when he removes reference to Sunnī scholars, for instance. It is arguably more accurate, however, to interpret that he is de-Sunnīfying it. Al-Ṭūsī apparently makes no reference to distinctly Shī'ī authorities throughout the treatise. Moreover, while al-Zarnūjī writes that 'the people of what is right—and they are the Sunnīs (*'ahl al-sunnah wa-l-jamā'ah*)—asked for what is right from God Almighty, the clear Truth, the Guide, the Protector, and so God Almighty guided them and protected them from misguidance',⁵⁸ pseudo-al-Ṭūsī merely relays something similar to the statement directly

56 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'līm al-muta'allim*, 99; al-ṬŪSĪ, *'Ādāb al-muta'allimīn*, 102: وكان في الزمان الأول يتعلمون الحرفة: ثم يتعلمون العلم، حتى لا يطعموا في أموال الناس *wa-kāna fī l-zamāni l-'awwali yata'allamūna l-hirfata thumma yata'allamūna l-'ilm, ḥattā lā yaṭma'ū fī 'amwāli l-nās.*

57 This contemporary observation from within the Shī'ī tradition's *hawzah* circles also makes it less likely that al-Ṭūsī (or another presumed author) was relying on the teacher explaining the text to include examples encouraging students to divide their time between work and studies.

58 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta'līm al-muta'allim*, 95: طلبوا الحق من الله تعالى، الحق المبين الهادي، العاصم، فهداهم الله تعالى، وعصمهم *ṭalabū l-haqqā min-a llāhi ta'ālā, al-haqq l-mubīn l-hādī l-'āsim, fa-hadāhum-u llāhu ta'ālā, wa-'aṣamahum 'an-i l-ḍalāla.*

preceding it: ‘[the learner should seek success and] guidance from God [...], for indeed God Almighty guides the one who seeks [His] guidance’,⁵⁹ and does not add anything particularly Shī‘ī. This indicates that pseudo-al-Ṭūsī was writing the treatise for wide circulation, to be suitable for the formation of learner subjects across sectarian boundaries. In this model for reading the treatise, the author of *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn* might as well have been a Sunnī author whose aim was to shape learners into aiming for being among ‘the people of what is right’, but without wishing for those learners to take it as a preconceived notion that one sectarian affiliation or another necessarily entailed that one was or was not among them. The emphasis of this reading is, then, in how the treatise(s) would be anticipated to function in their respective circles of circulation, not so much the actual intent of the authors or their sectarian identity.

Conclusion

Analyzing the differences between the two treatises illustrates that [pseudo-] al-Ṭūsī’s *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn* is invested in the formation of a specialized type of learner who is arguably less impacted by the sectarian identity of scholarly examples and is, rather, concerned with observing the etiquette and cultivating the underlying ethic. This anticipated function is often read in between the lines of omissions, rather than additions. Whether or not al-Ṭūsī consciously intended it (or even wrote the treatise himself) is of little significance once the interventions are convincingly interpreted to have (or likely have) such a function. Just as al-Zarnūjī’s *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*’s elaborations and examples can have formative functions allowing certain etiquettes to ‘hit home’ in ways that *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*’s brevity lacks, so *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*’s omissions and modifications allow other etiquettes to hit home without being associated with a particular sectarian identity. Among the conclusions to be drawn from this analysis, then, is that we have here an instance of post-Mongol invasion ‘confessional ambiguity,’ not through a display of ‘Alid loyalism (as is arguably prevalent during the Later Middle Period of Islamic history), but in the apparently deliberate removal of Sunnī-specific references.⁶⁰

59 al-ZARNŪJĪ, *Ta’līm al-muta’allim*, 95; al-ṬŪSĪ, *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn*, 100: ويطلب من الله التوفيق والهداية ، فإن الله تعالى هاد لمن استهداه *wa-yaṭluba min-a llāhi l-tawfiqa wa-l-hidāyah, fa-inna llāha ta’ālā hādīn li-man-i stahdāh.*

60 For a discussion of confessional ambiguity vs. polarization during this period, see: Judith PFEIFFER, ‘Confessional ambiguity vs. confessional polarization: politics and the negotiation of religious boundaries in the Ilkhanate’ in Judith PFEIFFER (ed.), *Politics, Patronage and the Transmission of Knowledge in 13th–15th Century Tabriz*, Leiden: Brill, 2014), 129–68. Pfeiffer follows John E. Woods in the use of the term ‘confessional ambiguity’ in this context. See John E. WOODS, *The Aqqyunlu: Clan, Confederation, Empire*, revised and expanded edition, Salt Lake City/UT: University of Utah Press, 1999: 4. – Evaluating the broader narratives of these studies would go beyond the scope of this article, but the present analysis of the *’Ādāb al-muta’allimīn* treatise can contribute to addressing them in future studies.

Acknowledgements

This article developed out of an independent study project translating and commenting on the *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn* treatise, beginning in the Spring of 2016 at Columbia University. I thank Brinkley Messick for his comments during those initial discussions and subsequent engagement. Correspondence with Hossein Modarressi on an earlier draft of this paper also honed its analysis, particularly on the attribution to al-Ṭūsī, for which I am grateful. Sketches of the *Ḥawzah* description were first presented at Columbia’s Sharīʿa workshop in October 2020. Special gratitude to my professors and colleagues, as well as those unnamed or anonymous, to whom credit is due for these findings in ways that are underacknowledged or unrecognized.

Bibliography

- AFANDI, Mochtar. 1993. “The Method of Muslim Learning as Illustrated in al-Zarnuji’s Ta’lim al-Mutaʿallim Tariq al-Taʿallum.” M.A. thesis, McGill University.
- ĀL QĀSIM, ʿAdnān Farḥān. 2016. *Tārīkh al-ḥawzāt al-ʿilmiyyah wa-l-madāris al-dīniyyah ʿind al-shīʿah al-ʿimāmiyyah*. 1st ed., 6 vols. Vol. 1. Beirut: Sharikat Dār al-Salām.
- AL-ʿAʿRĀFĪ, ʿAlī Riḍā, ʿAlī al-KHĀMINAʿĪ, Jaʿfar al-SUBHĀNĪ, Nāṣir MAKĀRIM al-SHĪRĀZĪ, ʿAbd Allāh JAWĀDĪ al-ĀMULĪ, et al. May 7-8, 2025. “[Conference Proceedings].” In *Muʿtamar al-Dhikrā al-miʿawīya li-ʿādat taʿsīs al-ḥawzah al-ʿilmiyyah fī Qom*. Qom: Wikālat Anbāʾ al-Ḥawzah. <https://ar.hawzahnews.com/photo/372945/المؤتمر-الذكري-المتوية-لإعادة-تأسيس-الحوزة-العلمية-في-قم>.
- al-BAHĀDLĪ, ʿAlī Aḥmad. 1993. *Al-Ḥawzah al-ʿilmiyyah fī l-Najaf: maʿālimuhā wa-ḥarakatuhā al-ʿislāhiyyah*. 1st ed. Beirut: Dār al-Zahrāʾ lil-ṭibāʿah wa-l-nashr wa-l-tawzīʿ.
- BAHR al-ʿULŪM, Muḥammad ʿAlī. 2025. *Ṣafahāt min tārīkh al-ḥawzah (Āl Bahr al-ʿUlūm)* | Podcast bi-tawqīt al-Najaf. Interview by Akram al-MURAWWIJ. Accessed May 22, 2025. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hVzMaQpe4FI>.
- EP³ = Encyclopædia of Islam, THREE*, edited by Kate FLEET, Gudrun KRÄMER, Denis MATRINGE, John NAWAS, and E. ROWSON. Leiden: Brill, 2017.
- GÜNTHER, Sebastian. 2016. “‘Your Educational Achievements Shall Not Stop Your Efforts to Seek Beyond’ Principles of Teaching and Learning in Classical Arabic Writings.” In ZAMAN & MEMON (eds.) 2016: 72–93.
- . 2017. “Education, General (up to 1500).” In *EP³*. doi: https://doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_ei3_COM_26134.
- (ed.). 2020. *Knowledge and Education in Classical Islam: Religious Learning between Continuity and Change*. 2 vols. Leiden: Brill.
- al-ḤANĀFĪ (d. 1078/1667), Riyāḍ Zādeh. *Asmāʾ al-kutub al-mutammim li-Kashf al-Zunūn*. Edited by Muḥammad al-Tūnjī. 3rd ed. Damascus: Dār al-Fikr, 1983.
- al-ḤUSAYNĪ al-KHAṬĪB, ʿAbd al-Zahrāʾ. *Maṣādir Nahj al-Balāghah wa-ʿasānīduh*. 4th ed., 4 vols. Beirut: Dār al-Zahrāʾ, 1988.
- IBN ʿABD AL-ḤĀQQ al-Baghdādī (d. 739/1338), ʿAbd al-Muʿmin. *Marāṣid al-iṭṭilāʿ ʿalā ʿasmāʾ al-ʿamkinah wa-l-biqāʿ*. Edited by ʿAlī Muḥammad al-BAJĀWĪ. 3 vols. Vol. 2. Beirut: Dār al-Jīl, 1992.

- al-JAWHARĪ (d. 393/1003), Ismā'īl b. Ḥammād. *Tāj al-lughah wa-ṣiḥāḥ al-ʿarabiyyah*. Edited by Aḥmad ʿAbd al-Ghafūr ʿATTĀR. 4th ed., 6 vols. Vol. 3. Cairo: Dār al-ʿIlm lil-Malāyīn, 1987.
- KEMPER, Michael, and Ralf ELGER (eds.). 2017. *The Piety of Learning: Islamic Studies in Honor of Stefan Reichmuth*. Leiden: Brill. (Islamic History and Civilization).
- LAPIDUS, Ira M. 1984. "Knowledge, Virtue, and Action: The Classical Muslim Conception of Adab and the Nature of Religious Fulfillment in Islam." In METCALF (ed.) 1984: 38–61.
- METCALF, Barbara Daly (ed.). 1984. *Moral Conduct and Authority: The Place of Adab in South Asian Islam*. London: University of California Press, Ltd.
- MOAZZEN, Maryam. 2020. "Shīʿī Higher Learning in the Pre-Safavid Period: Scholars, Educational Ideals, Practices, and Curricula." In GÜNTHER (ed.) 2020, ii: 818–46.
- NOORI, Seyed Masoud, Aun H. ALI, Aria NAKISSA, and Ali MOUGHANIA. 2020. "Roundtable Discussion: The Ḥawzah and the Sharia." Presented at the Sharīʿah Workshop, Columbia University in the City of New York; Online, October 22, 2020.
- PATRIZI, Luca. 2020. "The Metaphor of the Divine Banquet and the Origin of the Notion of Adab." In GÜNTHER (ed.) 2020, i: 516–38.
- PFEIFFER, Judith. 2014. "Confessional Ambiguity vs. Confessional Polarization: Politics and the Negotiation of Religious Boundaries in the Ilkhanate." In EAD. (ed.) 2014: 129–68. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004262577_006.
- (ed.). 2014. *Politics, Patronage and the Transmission of Knowledge in 13th–15th Century Tabriz*. (Iran Studies; vol. 8). Leiden: Brill.
- al-QURASHĪ al-Ḥanafī (d. 775/1373), ʿAbd al-Qādir. *Al-Jawāhir al-muḍīyah fī ṭabaqāt al-ḥanafīyyah*. 2 vols. Karachi: Mīr Muḥammad Kutub Khānah, n.d.
- SALIBA, George. 2007. *Islamic Science and the Making of the European Renaissance*. Transformations: Studies in the History of Science and Technology. Cambridge, Massachusetts; London, England: MIT Press.
- . 1999. "Whose Science Was Arabic Science in Renaissance France?" <https://www.columbia.edu/~gas1/project/visions/case1/sci.1.html>.
- SEESMANN, Rüdiger. 2017. "ʿIlm and Adab Revisited: Knowledge Transmission and Character Formation in Islamic Africa." In KEMPER & ELGER (eds.) 2017: 15–37. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004349841_003.
- STEWART, Devin. 2010. "Notes on Zayn al-Dīn al-ʿĀmilī's *Munyat al-murīd fī ʿādāb al-muḥīd wa-l-mustafīd*." *Journal of Islamic Studies*, 21.2: 235–70.
- al-ṬABĀṬABĀʾĪ (d. 1402/1981), Muḥammad Ḥusayn. *Sunan al-Nabī (Ṣ)*. Edited by Muḥammad Hādī al-FIQHĪ. 3rd ed. Qom: Muʿassasat al-Nashr al-Islāmī, 1427 AH.
- al-ṬIHRĀNĪ, Āghā Buzurg. *Al-Dharīʿah ʿilā taṣānīf al-shīʿah*. 3rd ed., 26 vols. Vol. 1. Beirut: Dār al-Aḍwāʾ, 1983.
- al-ṬŪSĪ (d. 672/1274), Naṣīr al-Dīn. *ʿĀdāb al-mutaʿallimīn*. Edited by Muḥammad Riḍā al-JALĀLĪ. 1st ed. Shīrāz: Intishārāt-i Kitābkhāna-i Madrasa-i ʿIlmiyyah-i Imām-i ʿAṣr, 1416AH.
- VON GRUNEBaum, Gustave Edmund (transl.) → ZARNŪJĪ, Burhān al-Dīn.
- WOODS, John E. 1999. *The Aqqyunlu: Clan, Confederation, Empire*. Revised and expanded ed. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.
- YĀQŪṬ Ibn ʿAbd Allāh al-Ḥamawī (d. 626/1229). *Muʿjam al-buldān*. 5 vols. Vol. 3. Beirut: Dār Iḥyāʾ al-Turāth al-ʿArabī, 1979.

Learning Etiquette History

- ZAMAN, Mujadad, and Nadeem A. MEMON (eds.). 2016. *Philosophies of Islamic Education*. New York: Routledge.
- al-ZARNŪJĪ (d. ca 640/1242), Burhān al-Islām. *Ta'lim al-muta'allim*. Edited by Ṣalāḥ Muḥammad al-KHAYMĪ and Nadhīr ḤAMDĀN. 3rd ed. Beirut: Dār Ibn Kathīr, 2014.
- ZARNŪJĪ, Burhān al-Dīn. *Instruction of the Student*. Translated by Gustave Edmund VON GRUNEBaum. New York: King's Crown Press, 1947.
- ZAYN al-'ĀBIDĪN al-SAJJĀD (d. 95/713), 'Alī b. al-Ḥusayn. *Al-Ṣaḥīfah al-Sajjādiyyah al-kāmilah*. Edited by Muḥammad Bāqir al-ṢADR. Beirut: Mu'assasat al-A'lamī lil-Maṭbū'āt, n.d.

© Ali Moughania, Ph.D. Columbia University in the City of New York, USA

◀ anm2168@columbia.edu ▶

Page | 107